

Medicine and comprehensive treatment of hypertension: drug and non-drug therapy

Medicina y tratamiento integral de la hipertensión: farmacoterapia y no farmacoterapia

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Abstract

The article discusses in detail modern methods of complex treatment of hypertension, which occupies one of the leading places among the causes of disability and mortality worldwide. Hypertension is characterised by a sustained increase in blood pressure, which in the long term leads to damage to vital organs such as the heart, kidneys, brain and blood vessels. Therefore, timely and effective therapy is a key aspect in the fight against this disease.

Drug treatment of hypertension is the mainstay of therapy, and this article provides an in-depth analysis of the pharmacological groups that are used in practice. Such drugs as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors, angiotensin receptor blockers (sartans), beta-adrenergic blockers, calcium channel blockers, and thiazide and loop diuretics are considered. The mechanisms of action of each group, their effect on blood pressure, as well as side effects and contraindications are described. The data of clinical studies confirming the effectiveness of various therapy regimens, including the combination of drugs to achieve a stable reduction in blood pressure are given.

In addition, considerable attention is paid to non-medication therapy of hypertension, which is an important adjunct to drug treatment. The article emphasizes the need to change the patient's lifestyle, which includes nutritional correction, reducing salt intake, maintaining a normal level of physical activity, controlling body weight and avoiding bad habits such as smoking and alcohol abuse. The principles of rational nutrition in hypertension are discussed, including the DASH diet, which is rich in vegetables, fruit, whole grains and low-fat dairy products and has been shown to be effective in reducing blood pressure.

Psychotherapeutic approaches such as cognitive-behavioral therapy and relaxation techniques that can reduce stress, an important factor in the development of hypertension, are also discussed. Modern physical rehabilitation techniques, including physical therapy, aerobic exercise and yoga, are discussed to help normalize blood pressure and improve patients' general well-being.

The article pays special attention to a personalized approach to the treatment of hypertension. The author

emphasizes that the choice of drug therapy should be based not only on blood pressure levels, but also on the presence of co morbidities, patient's age and individual tolerance to drugs. A comprehensive approach to the treatment of hypertension, which combines drug and non-drug therapy, allows not only to effectively control blood pressure, but also to prevent the development of complications such as myocardial infarction, stroke, heart and renal failure.

Thus, the article emphasizes the importance of an integrated approach in the management of hypertension, which requires the active participation of both the physician and the patient to achieve long-term positive results and improved quality of life.

Keywords: hypertension, arterial hypertension, drug therapy, non-drug therapy, ACE inhibitors, calcium channel blockers, diuretics, lifestyle modification, DASH diet, physical activity, prevention of complications, cardiovascular disease, blood pressure control.

El artículo analiza en detalle los métodos modernos de tratamiento complejo de la hipertensión, que ocupa uno de los primeros lugares entre las causas de discapacidad y mortalidad en todo el mundo. La hipertensión se caracteriza por un aumento sostenido de la presión arterial, que a largo plazo provoca daños en órganos vitales como el corazón, los riñones, el cerebro y los vasos sanguíneos. Por tanto, una terapia oportuna y eficaz es un aspecto clave en la lucha contra esta enfermedad.

El tratamiento farmacológico de la hipertensión es la base de la terapia y este artículo proporciona un análisis en profundidad de los grupos farmacológicos que se utilizan en la práctica. Se consideran fármacos como los inhibidores de la enzima convertidora de angiotensina (ECA), los bloqueadores de los receptores de angiotensina (sartán), los betabloqueantes, los bloqueadores de los canales de calcio y las tiazidas y los diuréticos de asa. Se describen los mecanismos de acción de cada grupo, su efecto sobre la presión arterial, así como los efectos secundarios y contraindicaciones. Se proporcionan datos de estudios clínicos que confirman la eficacia de diversos regímenes terapéuticos, incluida la combinación de fármacos, para lograr una reducción estable de la presión arterial.

Además, se presta considerable atención al tratamiento no farmacológico de la hipertensión, que es un complemento importante del tratamiento farmacológico. El artículo enfatiza la necesidad de cambiar el estilo de vida del paciente, que incluye corrección nutricional, reducción del consumo de sal, mantenimiento de un nivel normal de actividad física, control del peso corporal y evitar malos hábitos como el tabaquismo y el abuso de alcohol. Se analizan los principios de una nutrición racional en la hipertensión, incluida la dieta DASH, que es rica en verduras, frutas, cereales integrales y productos lácteos bajos en grasa y ha demostrado ser eficaz para reducir la presión arterial.

También se analizan enfoques psicoterapéuticos como la terapia cognitivo-conductual y técnicas de relajación que pueden reducir el estrés, un factor importante en el desarrollo de la hipertensión. Se analizan las técnicas modernas de rehabilitación física, incluida la fisioterapia, el ejercicio aeróbico y el yoga, para ayudar a normalizar la presión arterial y mejorar el bienestar general de los pacientes.

El artículo presta especial atención a un enfoque personalizado del tratamiento de la hipertensión. El autor subraya que la elección del tratamiento farmacológico debe basarse no sólo en los niveles de presión arterial, sino también en la presencia de comorbilidades, la edad del paciente y la tolerancia individual a los fármacos. Un enfoque integral para el tratamiento de la hipertensión, que combina terapia farmacológica y no farmacológica, permite no solo controlar eficazmente la presión arterial, sino también prevenir el desarrollo de complicaciones como infarto de miocardio, accidente cerebrovascular, insuficiencia cardíaca y renal.

Así, el artículo enfatiza la importancia de un enfoque integrado en el manejo de la hipertensión, que requiere la participación activa tanto del médico como del paciente para lograr resultados positivos a largo plazo y una mejor calidad de vida.

Palabras clave: hipertensión, hipertensión arterial, farmacoterapia, terapia no farmacológica, inhibidores de la ECA, bloqueadores de los canales de calcio, diuréticos, modificación del estilo de vida, dieta DASH, actividad física, prevención de complicaciones, enfermedad cardiovascular, control de la presión arterial.

Introduction

Hypertension (arterial hypertension) is one of the most common chronic diseases affecting the health of millions of people worldwide. According to the World Health Organization, hypertension is the leading risk factor for cardiovascular disease and stroke, as well as a cause of significant disability and premature mortality¹. Constantly high blood pressure causes damage to various organs, including the heart, kidneys and brain, which can lead to serious complications such as heart failure, heart attack and stroke.

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The treatment of hypertension requires a comprehensive approach that includes both drug and non-drug therapy. Drug treatment aims to lower blood pressure using different classes of antihypertensive drugs such as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors, beta-blockers and calcium channel blockers. At the same time, non-pharmacological methods, including lifestyle modification, dietary advice and physical activity, play an equally important role in managing the disease and preventing its complications.

The aim of this article is to analyze current approaches to the comprehensive treatment of hypertension, to evaluate the effectiveness of different methods, and to consider the significance of integrating drug and non-drug therapy to achieve stable blood pressure control and improve the quality of life of patients. The article will present current research, recommendations and practical aspects that will help healthcare professionals in choosing the optimal strategy for the treatment of hypertension.

Materials and methods

Various theoretical methods were used to investigate the problem of complex treatment of hypertension, which allowed us to gain a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of the disease, evaluate the effectiveness of therapeutic approaches, and develop recommendations for clinical practice. Systematic analyses of existing studies on drug and non-drug therapies for hypertension included meta-analyses, clinical trials, and systematic reviews. It also compared different treatment approaches, the efficacy of antihypertensive drugs and non-pharmacological methods, and case studies of hypertensive patients to evaluate the results of different treatment regimens.

Results

Hypertension (arterial hypertension) is a multifactorial disease that requires a comprehensive approach to treatment. Sustained elevation of blood pressure usually does not cause obvious symptoms in the initial stages, which often leads to late seeking medical attention. However, in the long term, high blood pressure causes a number of serious pathological changes in the body².

Hypertension leads to increased stress on the heart, which can cause left ventricular hypertrophy. This condition increases the risk of heart failure, arrhythmias and coronary heart disease. Chronic hypertension can also contribute to the development of coronary artery disease and increases the likelihood of myocardial infarction.

High blood pressure has a negative effect on the kidneys, leading to nephrosclerosis and chronic renal failure. Pathological changes in the renal vessels impair their function, which can cause oedema, electrolyte imbalances and the need for dialysis.

Hypertension is a major risk factor for stroke. High blood pressure leads to damage to cerebral blood vessels, which can cause both ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes. Chronic hypertension is also associated with cognitive impairment and dementia³.

A sustained increase in blood pressure causes accelerated atherosclerosis, which increases the risk of thrombosis and cardiovascular disease. Damage to the vascular wall can lead to the formation of aneurysms and other dangerous conditions.

Timely and effective therapy of hypertension is critical to prevent disease progression and reduce the risk of complications. Comprehensive treatment includes both medication and non-medication methods, which allows for a maximally individualized approach to each patient⁴.

Drug treatment of hypertension represents a fundamental element in the management of this chronic disease, aimed at reducing and maintaining normal blood pres-

sure. As part of a comprehensive approach to the therapy of hypertension, several key pharmacological groups are identified, each with their own mechanisms of action, indications and side effects.

Table 1 presents the main pharmacological groups of antihypertensive drugs, their mechanisms of action, examples, indications and side effects.

Table 1. The main pharmacological groups of antihypertensive drugs, their mechanisms of action, examples, indications and side effects.

Pharmacological group	Mechanism of action	Examples	Indications	Side effects
ACE inhibitors	Block the conversion of angiotensin I to angiotensin II	Enalapril, Lisinopril, Ramipril	Hypertension, heart failure, kidney protection in diabetes	Cough, hyperkalemia, angioedema
Angiotensin receptor blockers	Block the action of angiotensin II on receptors	Losartan, Valsartan, Irbesartan.	Hypertension, heart failure	Hyperkalemia, dizziness, angioedema
Beta-adrenoblockers	Reduce the frequency and strength of heartbeats	Atenolol, Metoprolol, Bisoprolol	Hypertension, angina pectoris, after myocardial infarction	Fatigue, slow heart rate, bronchospasm.
Calcium channel blockers	Reduce the entry of calcium into the cells of blood vessels and the heart	Amlodipine, Diltiazem, Nifedipine	Hypertension, angina pectoris, some types of arrhythmias	Swelling, headache, hot flashes, constipation
Diuretics	Increase sodium and water excretion, reducing circulating blood volume	Hydrochlorothiazide, Furosemide, Spironolactone	Hypertension, oedema syndrome, heart failure	Hypokalaemia, dehydration, hypotension

ACE inhibitors aim to block the action of angiotensin-converting enzyme, which leads to a decrease in the level of angiotensin II, a substance that causes vasoconstriction and an increase in blood pressure. These drugs prevent the conversion of angiotensin I (which has no significant activity) into angiotensin II, which is a powerful vasoconstrictor. This leads to vasodilation, lowering vascular resistance and therefore lowering blood pressure. Additionally, ACE inhibitors help to reduce cardiac workload and improve renal function⁵.

Examples of drugs from this group include Enalapril, Lisinopril and Ramipril. These drugs are widely used in clinical practice and have different pharmacokinetic properties and duration of action, allowing the most appropriate options to be selected for specific patients.

ACE inhibitors are indicated for various clinical conditions such as hypertension, heart failure and renal protection in diabetes. They help to lower blood pressure, reduce cardiac workload and prevent the development of diabetic nephropathy by reducing intracubular pressure⁶.

Like any medication, ACE inhibitors can cause side effects. These include coughing, which is a common side effect due to bradykinin accumulation; Hyperkalemia, which can be dangerous to your health; and angioedema, a rare but potentially life-threatening condition manifested by swelling of the face, lips and throat.

Thus, ACE inhibitors play an important role in the treatment of hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases.

They are one of the main classes of drugs recommended for blood pressure control and target organ protection. Their mechanisms of action, indications and side effects make them a key tool in the armory of cardiologists and general practitioners.

Angiotensin receptor blockers, also known as sartans, aim to block the action of angiotensin II on its receptors. This causes blood vessels to dilate and blood pressure to drop. Drugs in this group work by preventing angiotensin II from binding to receptors on vascular smooth muscle cells, which helps to relax blood vessels and reduce overall vascular resistance.

Examples of drugs from this group include Losartan, Valsartan and Irbesartan. These drugs are widely used in clinical practice and have different pharmacokinetic properties, what allows choosing the most appropriate one for a particular patient⁷.

Angiotensin receptor blockers are indicated for a variety of conditions, including hypertension and heart failure. They can also be used to prevent and treat kidney failure in diabetic patients, as they help to reduce intrarenal pressure and protect the kidneys from damage.

In terms of side effects, sartans have a more favorable profile compared to ACE inhibitors. Nevertheless, they may cause Hyperkalemia, dizziness and, in rare cases, angioedema. Hyperkalemia may be particularly dangerous in patients with impaired renal function⁸.

Accordingly, angiotensin receptor blockers are an important part of the therapy of hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases. They provide effective blood pressure lowering and target organ protection, making them an important tool in the treatment of this pathology. Due to their mechanisms of action and safety profile, sartans are becoming increasingly popular among doctors and patients.

Beta-adrenoblockers are a class of antihypertensive drugs that reduce heart rate and heart force. They block the action of adrenaline and nor epinephrine on beta-adrenoreceptors located in the heart, lungs and blood vessels. This results in a decrease in cardiac output and blood pressure. Beta-adrenoblockers are particularly effective in controlling blood pressure in patients with co morbidities such as angina pectoris and heart failure.

Examples of drugs in this group include Atenolol, Metoprolol and Bisoprolol. These drugs differ in their selectivity to beta-1 and beta-2 adrenoreceptors, which allows physicians to choose the most appropriate drug for a particular patient depending on the patient's condition and the presence of co morbidities⁹.

Beta-adrenoblockers are indicated for hypertension, angina pectoris, post-myocardial infarction and heart failure. They can also be used to prevent migraine and control anxiety, making them versatile agents in cardiology.

Despite their effectiveness, beta-adrenoblockers can cause a number of side effects. The most common of these include fatigue, slow heart rate and bronchospasm, especially in patients with a predisposition to asthma or obstructive pulmonary disease. Metabolic disorders such as weight gain and dyslipidaemia may also occur¹⁰.

Beta-adrenoblockers are an important group of antihypertensive drugs with multiple indications and mechanisms of action. They effectively control blood pressure and improve prognosis in patients with cardiovascular disease. However, their prescription requires careful assessment of the patient's condition and possible side effects, which underlines the importance of an individualized approach in the treatment of hypertension.

Calcium channel blockers are a class of antihypertensive drugs that reduce the flow of calcium ions into vascular and cardiac smooth muscle cells. Calcium plays a key role in muscle contraction, including vascular smooth muscle. When calcium channel blockers restrict calcium entry into cells, it leads to relaxation of the vascular wall, dilating blood vessels and lowering blood pressure. In heart cells, they can also reduce heart rate and heart force, which is useful in the treatment of some arrhythmias and angina pectoris.

Examples of drugs include Amlodipine, Diltiazem and Nifedipine. Calcium channel blockers are divided into two main groups: dihydropyridines (e.g. Amlodipine), which mainly act on the blood vessels, and non-dihydropyridines (e.g. Diltiazem), which affect the heart. This

division allows the drugs to be used depending on the clinical situation: dihydropyridines are preferred in arterial hypertension, while nondihydropyridines may be useful in arrhythmias¹¹.

Calcium channel blockers are indicated for arterial hypertension, angina pectoris and some types of arrhythmias. They are particularly effective in patients with increased vascular stiffness (e.g. the elderly) and in the presence of co-morbidities such as coronary heart disease.

However, like any medication, calcium channel blockers can cause side effects. Common side effects are leg swelling, headaches and hot flashes, which are associated with vasodilation. In addition, constipation may occur, especially with some members of this group. Nondihydropyridine blockers may cause bradycardia (slowing of the heart rate) and worsening of cardiac conduction, therefore they are used with caution in patients with heart failure.

Diuretics are a class of drugs aimed at increasing the excretion of sodium and water through the kidneys, which reduces the volume of circulating blood and, consequently, blood pressure. The mechanism of their action is based on blocking sodium reabsorption in renal tubules, which increases the amount of fluid excreted with urine and reduces the load on the cardiovascular system¹².

Examples of diuretics include Hydrochlorothiazide, Furosemide and Spironolactone. These drugs fall into several subgroups: thiazide diuretics (e.g. Hydrochlorothiazide) are most commonly used for the long-term treatment of hypertension, loop diuretics (e.g. Furosemide) are used for their rapid and strong diuretic effect in oedema, and potassium-saving diuretics (e.g. Spironolactone) are prescribed to prevent potassium loss, making them particularly useful in combination with other diuretics.

Diuretics are indicated for arterial hypertension, heart failure and oedema syndromes such as oedema caused by heart, liver or kidney disease. They play an important role in controlling blood pressure, especially in patients with fluid retention, and help to reduce symptoms of heart failure.

However, side effects can occur with diuretics. One of the most common is hyperglycemia (decreased blood potassium levels), which can cause muscle weakness, arrhythmias and other complications. To prevent this condition, potassium-saving diuretics are often used or diuretics are combined with drugs that prevent potassium loss¹². It is also possible to develop dehydration and too great a drop in blood pressure (hypotension), especially when using potent loop diuretics. Some patients may develop metabolic disorders such as hyperglycemia and hyperglycemia, which is important to consider in concomitant diseases such as diabetes mellitus or gout.

In conclusion, diuretics are an important part of the therapy of hypertension and cardiovascular diseases.

They effectively reduce blood pressure by reducing the volume of circulating fluid and eliminate oedema, improving the patient's general condition. However, their use requires monitoring of electrolyte balance and renal function, which makes regular monitoring of the patient's condition an important part of treatment.

Non-drug therapy of hypertension plays an important role in complex treatment and can significantly increase the effectiveness of drug intervention. In some cases, lifestyle changes and the introduction of non-medication approaches can lead to significant reductions in blood pressure, reduced dosage of drugs or even their withdrawal in patients with early stages of the disease.

One of the key aspects is to reduce salt intake, as excess sodium contributes to fluid retention in the body and increases blood pressure. It is recommended to limit salt intake to 5-6 grams per day. It is also important to increase the intake of potassium, magnesium and calcium, which are found in vegetables, fruits and dairy products. It is useful to follow the principles of the DASH (Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension) diet, which is rich in plant foods, whole grains and healthy fats.

Overweight and obesity are among the main risk factors for hypertension. A 5-10% reduction in body weight can lead to a significant reduction in blood pressure. It is important to maintain a moderate caloric intake and regular physical activity to achieve and maintain a normal weight¹³.

Regular physical activity of moderate intensity (e.g. walking, swimming, and cycling) improves vascular tone, reduces stress and strengthens the cardiovascular system. It is recommended that at least 30 minutes a day, 5-7 times a week, should be devoted to physical activity.

Smoking has a negative effect on blood vessels, accelerating atherosclerosis and increasing the risk of cardiovascular accidents. Smoking cessation helps to improve the overall vascular health and reduce blood pressure. Moderate alcohol consumption (up to 30 ml of ethanol per day for men and up to 20 ml for women) can also be beneficial, but excessive alcohol consumption has a negative effect on blood pressure.

Stress is one of the factors contributing to the development and exacerbation of hypertension. Relaxation techniques such as meditation, yoga, breathing exercises and psychotherapy can help reduce stress and control blood pressure.

Lack of sleep and its poor quality can contribute to the development of hypertension. It is important to ensure a good night's sleep (at least 7-8 hours per night) and normalize the daily routine to maintain cardiovascular health.

Thus, non-medication therapy of hypertension is an important complement to drug treatment. It is aimed at eliminating risk factors and adjusting lifestyle, which

not only reduces blood pressure but also improves the patient's general health. A comprehensive approach, including dietary changes, physical activity and stress management, increases the chances of successful control of the disease and reduction of its complications.

Discussion

Psychotherapeutic approaches play a significant role in non-pharmacological therapy of hypertension, as emotional stress is one of the key factors provoking the development and exacerbation of hypertension. Among the psychotherapeutic methods most effective in reducing stress levels are cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and relaxation techniques.

CBT is one of the most effective approaches in psychotherapy for changing negative patterns of thinking and behaviour that contribute to chronic stress and high blood pressure. CBT helps patients:

- identify and recognize stressors and one's own automatic negative thoughts that can increase anxiety and worry;
- develop new strategies for managing stress and emotional responses to difficult situations;
- develop healthier behavioral patterns and self-regulation skills, such as recognizing and controlling one's emotions, improving communication skills and problem solving¹⁴.

Studies show that CBT helps to reduce anxiety and depression, which in turn can have a positive effect on blood pressure. Psychological interventions can improve a patient's overall well-being, reduce internal tension and increase coping skills without harming health.

Relaxation techniques are aimed at reducing the body's physiological and emotional reactivity to stress. These techniques help to reduce the activation of the sympathetic nervous system, which is responsible for the "hit or run" response that leads to high blood pressure. The main relaxation techniques applicable to the treatment of hypertension include:

- Controlled, slow breathing helps to activate the parasympathetic nervous system, which helps to reduce stress and blood pressure. For example, deep diaphragmatic breathing techniques reduce cortisol levels and normalize heart rate¹⁵.
- Meditation, including mindfulness meditation (mindfulness), teaches you to focus on the present moment

and not dwell on stressful thoughts. Regular meditation practice reduces stress levels, reduces anxiety and helps to control physiological responses to stressful situations.

Progressive muscle relaxation involves alternately tensing and relaxing different muscle groups to help relieve muscle tension and reduce stress levels. It also helps to improve self-awareness and relaxation.

Autogenic training helps patients to control their physiological processes, such as heart rate and blood pressure, by focusing on the sensations of warmth and heaviness in the body¹⁶.

Regular use of CBT and relaxation techniques in the treatment of hypertension helps to reduce sympathetic nervous system activity, normalise levels of stress hormones (such as cortisol) and improve the general state of the nervous system. In combination with medication, they allow better control of blood pressure, increase resistance to stressful situations and improve the patient's quality of life.

Thus, cognitive-behavioral therapy and relaxation techniques are important components of non-pharmacological therapy of hypertension, which help to cope with emotional factors that contribute to high blood pressure. Their use contributes to improving the patient's mental and physical health, reducing the risk of complications and improving the overall prognosis.

A personalized approach to the treatment of hypertension is a key element of successful therapy, as arterial hypertension can manifest itself differently in each patient and be associated with individual risk factors, health status, lifestyle and genetic predisposition. The goal of a personalized approach is to find the most effective treatment options, taking into account the unique characteristics of each patient.

For the correct choice of treatment, it is important to consider the patient's age, gender, presence of co morbidities (such as diabetes, ischemic heart disease, renal failure), level of physical activity and family history of cardiovascular disease. These factors influence the pattern of the course of hypertension and the choice of therapy. For example, diabetic patients need drugs that not only lower blood pressure but also protect the kidneys¹⁷.

Modern methods of genetic testing can identify a patient's predisposition to hypertension or reaction to certain classes of drugs. This allows for more precise drug therapy, minimizing side effects and increasing the effectiveness of treatment. For example, some patients may have a genetic sensitivity to ACE inhibitors or calcium channel blockers.

A personalized approach requires the selection of drugs and treatments that take into account not only the reduction of blood pressure but also the protection of target or-

gans such as the heart, kidneys and brain. For example, patients with chronic heart failure may be indicated for beta-blockers, which not only lower blood pressure but also strengthen cardiac function. Patients with chronic kidney disease need drugs that preserve kidney function (e.g. ACE inhibitors or sartans)¹⁸.

One important objective of the personalized approach is to minimize side effects. To do this, treatment starts with choosing the drugs that are best tolerated by the patient. For example, if a patient has side effects with ACE inhibitors (e.g. cough), it is possible to switch to sartans, which have a similar mechanism of action but do not cause this side effect.

Non-drug therapies such as dietary intervention, increased physical activity and stress management should be tailored to the patient. For example, dietary recommendations can be adapted according to the patient's cultural preferences, level of physical activity and health status. It is important to choose an exercise and nutrition regime that is realistic and achievable for the individual patient to ensure long-term adherence to recommendations.

A personalized approach also involves continuous monitoring of the patient's condition and adjusting treatment as needed. The use of modern technologies, such as home blood pressure monitoring and telemedicine, helps to make timely changes in therapy, which provides more accurate control of hypertension¹⁹.

Including psychological support in the treatment plan is also part of a personalized approach. For patients with high levels of stress or anxiety disorders, cognitive behavioral therapy and relaxation techniques may be recommended. These methods help to improve the patient's emotional well-being and contribute to better blood pressure control²⁰.

A personalized approach to the treatment of hypertension focuses on the individual needs of the patient. It involves a comprehensive consideration of all factors influencing the disease, such as genetics, co morbidities, lifestyle and psychological state. This approach allows not only to effectively control blood pressure, but also to reduce the risk of complications, improve the quality of life and extend the patient's life expectancy.

Hypertension is a complex and multifactorial disease that requires a comprehensive approach to treatment. Timely diagnosis and effective treatment of hypertension are important to prevent serious complications such as stroke, myocardial infarction, renal failure and heart failure. The following key findings were made in analyzing different therapies:

Drug treatment is the basis of therapy of hypertension. The use of different pharmacological groups (ACE inhibitors, angiotensin II receptor antagonists, calcium channel blockers, beta-adrenoblockers and diuretics) allows effective blood pressure control and reduces the risk of complications.

The choice of medication is based on the individual characteristics of the patient, the presence of co morbidities and tolerability of drugs.

Non-medication therapy is an important adjunct to drug treatment. Lifestyle changes, including dietary adjustments, weight reduction, regular physical activity, avoidance of unhealthy habits and stress management, have a significant impact on improving the patient's condition and controlling hypertension. Non-medicamentous methods can help to reduce the dosage of medications or even eliminate them in the early stages of the disease.

Techniques such as cognitive behavioral therapy and relaxation techniques have a significant impact on reducing stress levels, which is an important factor in the development of hypertension. Psychological support helps patients cope with the emotional and behavioral aspects of the disease, which contributes to more successful blood pressure control.

The treatment of hypertension should be individualized, taking into account the characteristics of each patient, such as genetic predisposition, co morbidities, and lifestyle and drug tolerance. Comprehensive monitoring and adjustment of therapy ensure more accurate blood pressure control and improved long-term treatment outcomes.

Thus, the treatment of hypertension requires a multifactorial and individualized approach, combining drug therapy with non-medication methods and psychotherapeutic support. Comprehensive treatment of the disease allows not only to stabilize blood pressure, but also to improve the quality of life of patients, minimizing the risk of complications.

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